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Research Article

Vibrational Study of Rhodamine 610 and Effect of Methanol on its Vibrational Spectra

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ABSTRACT

We report infrared and Raman spectra of Rhodamine 610 (Rh610) dye in powder form and in methanol. Positions of some of the observed vibrational bands show noticeable change in methanol. The bands, which shift, have contributions from the vibrational motion of nitrogen atoms of the diethylamine groups, oxygen atom of the carboxylic group attached to the phenyl ring and oxygen atom of the Xanthene ring.

Keywords: Laser dyes, FTIR spectra, Raman Spectra, Rh610.

INTRODUCTION

The vibrational spectroscopy is very helpful in providing valuable information about the bonding arrangement in a molecule. Raman and/or infrared (IR) spectroscopy can help in studying the vibrations of a molecule. Rhodamine dyes, a member of Xanthene class of laser dyes, have been of great interest among the researchers. They are used as active medium in tunable dye lasers, in single-molecule detection and various other applications Sasic et al (2005), Deshpande, Namdas (1996), Deshpande, Namdas (1997), Michaels et al (1999). The molecular structure, fluorescence and photo physics of rhodamine dyes are influenced by solvents. Solvent and water impurities effects on the structure and properties of rhodamine dyes have been studied by various optical spectroscopic techniques Arbeloa et al (1991), Arbeloa (1990), Sharma et al (2007). However, we have not come across any vibrational study on this particular aspect.

Bonding arrangements and changes induced by chemicals in structure/bonding of RhB molecule can be investigated from the study of IR and Raman spectra. These changes are expected to depend upon the nature of interacting chemicals. In the present work, we have studied the Raman and IR spectra of RhB in powder form and in methanol in order to investigate the effect of methanol on RhB molecule by observing the changes in the spectra. This study may provide a good understanding of the sensing properties of RhB and also the dependence of its fluorescence and, therefore, lasing property on methanol.

Experimental

The laser grade Rh610 from Exciton, USA was used without further purification. However, its purity was checked with electronic absorption spectroscopy. Spectroscopic grade methanol from Qualigens Fine Chemicals, India, was also used without any purification. The KBr pellet was used for obtaining the IR spectra of RhB crystalline powder. For recording of the IR spectra of the dye in methanol, few drops of solution of Rh610 (conc ~ 5×10^{-3} M) were put on a KBr window. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer PE-Rx1 FTIR Spectrophotometer. The normal Raman (NR) spectra were recorded on a LabRam JY HORIBA HR 800 spectrograph equipped with Olympus Bx41 microscope and ANDOR Model DU 420-0E-323 CCD detector. The measurements were carried out in a back scattering geometry with incident light linearly polarized and scattered light was detected unpolarized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structure of the Rh610 is shown in Figure 1. The IR spectra of Rh610 in the spectral range of 450-1800 cm^{-1} region are shown in the figure 2 under different experimental conditions. Normal Raman spectra of the dye powder and its solution in methanol are also shown in figure 3. The observed IR and Raman bands and their assignments are listed in table 1. The bands of RhB have been assigned with the help of already assigned bands of Rh6G as there is not much difference in their structures. The assignments of different bands are made on the basis of references Sarkar et al (2006), Watanabe et al (2005), Jensen, Schatz (2006). Some changes are observed in the IR and Raman spectra of Rh610 powder and the dye solution in methanol. Wave numbers of

certain bands have been shifted in the methanol. The change in band position is generally due to the change in force constant. We have also observed some changes in intensity of certain bands in solution compared to powder. Change in intensity is observed due to the change in overlap of vibrational wave functions of two states involved in transitions.

Figure 1. Structure and labeling of different groups of Rh 610.

Figure 2: Infrared spectra of Rh 610; (a) powder; (b) in methanol in $450\text{-}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Figure 3: Normal Raman spectra of Rh610 (a) in powder and (b) in methanol with 632.8 nm excitation.

Table1. Observed IR and Raman bands of RhB and their assignments

IR Bands Positions (cm ⁻¹) of Rh610 KBr Assignments*			Raman Band Positions (cm ⁻¹) of Rh610 Solid CH ₃ OH Assignments*		
		CH ₃ OH			
527			621	628	X+P
548	552		762	767	X+A
645	646	X+P	812	809	P
683	679	X	880	884	A
816	823	X+A+P	990	993	P
925	925	X+A+P	1028	1030	X+A+P
978	979	P	1093	1095	A
1010	1008	P	1200	1199	X+A+P
1077	1072	A+P	1236	1233	A+P
1132	1128	X+A	1258	1262	X+P
1180	1183	X+A	1302	1302	X+A
1245	1245	A+P	1361	1363	X+A
1270	1274	P	1424	1431	X
1337	1334	X+A	1505	1507	X+A
1417	1414	X	1526	1524	X+A
1463	1465	X+A	1556	1560	X+A
1513	1512	X+A	1591	1597	P
1554	1561	X+A	1648	1651	X
1583	1583	P	1686	1691	X
1644	1646	X	1714	1716	P
1699	1701	P	1731	1738	P

* Assignments of the bands are based on references Sarkar et al (2006), Watanabe et al (2005), Jensen, Schatz (2006).

The band at 1010 cm⁻¹ in IR spectra of Rh610 undergoes a downshift in methanol and appears at 1008 cm⁻¹. This band has vibrational contribution from P group. Downshift in this band is due to the interaction of C=O of P group with methanol molecules, which decreases the vibrational motion of P group and shifts the band to lower side of wave number.

The band at 1337 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of dye powder is assigned to vibrational motion of 'X' and 'A' group. This band shows a downshift in methanol solution and appears at 1334 cm⁻¹. This means that due to the interaction of oxygen atom of Xanthene ring and N-H of 'A' group of RhB with methanol, vibrational motion of 'X' and 'A' group of the dye decreases which downshifts the band.

In normal Raman spectra of the dye the band at 1648 cm⁻¹ gets an upshift in methanol and appears at 1651 cm⁻¹. This band appears due to the vibrational motion of 'X' ring. Upshift in the band suggested that due to the interaction of oxygen atom of X ring with methanol the electron density at Xanthene ring increases and the band gets an upshift in methanol.

So it is clear from the structure of RhB and above shift pattern that a number of interactions are possible between RhB molecule and methanol;

- Interaction involving central O atom of X ring, which can show hydrogen bonding with the solvent molecules
- Interaction involving C=O and OH of carboxylic acid group of P group
- Electrostatic interaction involving N atom due to positive charge

These interactions change the vibrational frequency of the motion of O and N atoms of 'P' and 'A' groups, respectively, and changes the electron density at a preferential site of the dye. The central O atom can also participate in hydrogen bonding interaction with methanol. Similarly, the possibility of hydrogen bonding interaction between the COOH of 'P' group of RhB with methanol cannot be ruled out.

CONCLUSIONS

Notable changes observed in the Raman and IR spectra of RhB in methanol compared to RhB powder arise due to various interactions taking place between RhB and methanol molecules in the solution. On the basis of band shift pattern it is concluded that methanol molecules interact with the N and/or H atoms of 'A' group and O atoms of X ring and 'P' group.

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